

The holy Anders of Slagelse

By Svend Clausen, TBC

Entry tags: Miracle tales, Christianity, Christian, Christianity, Religious Group, Catholic, Latin Text, Text, Hagiography, Medieval Christianity, Catholic text

The holy Anders of Slagelse was a Danish priest from the town of Slagelse. He became venerated as a saint in the area around Slagelse within Roskilde diocese in medieval Denmark after his death. Apparently he died in 1205. He was never officially canonized, but his cult remained popular amongst the people locally for centuries. This is pretty much all which is known about him. All other information preserved on him stems from his saint's legend and in this case the word legend really seems more appropriate than describing it as a saint's vita. Not much trustworthy information on his actual life is to be found in the text. Instead it takes on a highly legendary character full of fantastic tales clearly reflecting that this was stories told about him amongst the people orally and that they circulated like this for a very long time until they were finally written down. The preserved late medieval text does not even follow the normal structure of hagiography as there is e.g. no mention of posthumous miracles, nothing said about his childhood or youth and not even any translation description. The preserved text was transmitted to the present day because it was later copied by a chaplain called Jakob Mosle from a church in Slagelse sometime around 1500. Jakob Mosle is not the author of it, though, but instead states openly that he merely copied an older manuscript. How old exactly this older manuscript was is unknown, but it is clearly reflected in the text that it could not have been written until quite a long time after Anders had died. Only one piece of information slightly indicates the age of the written text. Jakob Mosle states the he copied the text from an old piece of paper. The use of paper in Denmark instead of parchment makes it unlikely that writing took place before c. the mid-14th century. Thus it seems that this text about the holy Anders must have been written down sometime after c. 1350, but well before Jakob Mosle copied it around 1500. The fact that these stories about him really did circulate orally already long before his preserved saint's legend was written down is known for certain, though, as an early version of one of these stories appear already in a book from around 1260 written by the Dominican friar Thomas of Cantimpré (1201-1272). Thomas of Cantimpré had probably heard this story from some anonymous Danish friar of his order, most likely a friar stemming from one of the friaries within Roskilde diocese. This Dominican book must be a story for another time, though, as the present entry will be about the text transmitted by Jakob Mosle exclusively.

Date Range: 1205 CE - 1536 CE

Region: Diocese of Roskilde, Denmark

Region tags: Denmark

Rough map of the medieval diocese of Roskilde during the late 12th and early 13th C. when the holy Anders lived here. He was also venerated here in the area around the town of Slagelse in the western part of mid-Zealand.

Status of Readership:

✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: M. CL. GERTZ: Vitae Sanctorum Danorum, Copenhagen, 1908-1912

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: https://wiki.app.uib.no/medieval/index.php?title=Sanctus_Andreas_Slavlosiensis

– Source 1 Description: Background information on the source in English

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: not available

General Variables

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– Yes

↳ Church

– Yes

Notes: Jakob Mosle stated that he copied the text from a manuscript that he found in St. Peders Church in Slagelse. It has been suggested that the original may have been some sort of memorial tablet.

Methods of Composition

– Written

↳ Inked

–with Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

↳ Specify type of paper

–Specify: Neither the medieval original nor Jakob Mosle's copy edition has been preserved. Today it is preserved in a few somewhat younger paper manuscripts probably going to the one by Jakob Mosle.

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– Field doesn't know

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

–Other [specify]: Not known as the original is not preserved.

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– Field doesn't know

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

–Other [specify]: Compared to hagiography in general it has a very loose structure. This does not suggest much preparation or intense modification, but rather indicates that it was simply oral stories written down.

Materiality

Methods of Composition

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Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– Field doesn't know

Production & Intended Audience

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Notes: As it seems to have been oral stories written down much later than they first appeared, there is nothing to suggest that the text was produced through official funding.

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The written version was probably meant mostly for the local clergy etc in the area, but the oral stories appear to have been widespread amongst the people of the diocese.

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

– No

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?

– Field doesn't know

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: It is written in latin

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

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Is there material significance to the text?

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Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: none of the above

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Notes: As e.g. in a story where the holy Anders visits the court of king Valdemar I of Denmark, when the king travelled through Slagelse. The king's henchmen laughs at him as he is dressed like a peasant, but Anders reprimands them and the king then orders them to treat him with respect.

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– Field doesn't know

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Notes: Although celibacy was required of Anders as a priest

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Notes: But the oral stories probably had variations and perhaps even multiple versions.

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– No

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– No

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– No

↳ Generosity/charity

– Yes

Notes: he gives away all of his bread to the poor, but then miraculously receives even more bread.

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

Notes: as in the story of the bread

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– No

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– No

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– No

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– No

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– No

↳ Cooperation

– No

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– No

↳ Moderation/frugality

– No

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– No

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– No

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– No

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

↳ Power/status/nobility

– No

↳ Humility/modesty

– Yes

Notes: In one story king Valdemar I of Denmark wants to give him a gift and Anders then asks for a necessary nearby field on behalf of the town of Slagelse. The king thinks that he asks of too little and then encourages him to ask of something more. Anders then also asks for a nearby stream.

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– No

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– No

↳ Optimism/hope

– No

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– No

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– No

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– Yes

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– No

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– No

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– No

↳ Other important virtues

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Notes: Although fasting is described in one of the stories in it.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dictated in the text?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

Notes: But yes to the extent that hagiography is also behavioral literature.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: On the surface it is hagiography, although it does not fit in very well structurally with that genre.

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Notes: Although the text does not explicitly formulate a calendar, it is likely to reflect that Anders was venerated on a specific date in the local church in Slagelse.

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

Notes: It describes how Anders prepared himself for his own death.

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– No

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– No

Notes: Although yes in the sense that one of it's fantastic miracle tales describes how he travelled from Jerusalem to Slagelse in Denmark in just one day by riding on a horse that he saw in a vision.

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Notes: Although yes if counting a visionary horse.

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Notes: Although for Anders as a priest it did

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– No

Notes: Although yes if counting the visionary horse.

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: the visionary horse

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Notes: Although the oral stories must have been for such purposes also.

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– Field doesn't know

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Notes: But the oral stories probably had variations and perhaps even multiple versions.

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

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Beliefs

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Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

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Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

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↳ Other important virtues
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Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?
– No

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?
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Notes: Although celibacy was required of Anders as a priest

Does the text require castration?
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Notes: Although fasting is described in one of the stories in it.

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Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– Other

Notes: A town church, although it was based on oral stories told amongst the local people.

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– Yes

Does the text in question dictate how the religious group in question provide food for themselves?

– No

↳ Does the text celebrate/restrict food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question?

– No

↳ Which of the follow are forms of ritual food production [choose all that apply]?

– Large-scale agriculture (E.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: Both farming and the brewing of beer is mentioned in the story where Anders receives the field and the stream from the king. The baking of bread is mentioned in another story where Anders miraculously heals an old blind woman and makes her able to see.

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Notes: although it does contain the story of Anders giving away all the bread.

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Notes: although the story of the bread is interesting in this regard too,.

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: none of the above

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: none of the above

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Notes: Although there is a story of Anders welcoming a crippled man into his home eventually healing him miraculously too.

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Society & Institutions

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Public Works

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Taxation

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Warfare

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General References

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